

STUDY ON THE SELECTION OF TECHNOLOGY FOR "VINAMIR" TABLETS**Khakimova K.U.¹****Yunusova Kh.M.²****Ilhamova N.B.²**

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Relevance: Import substitution is one of the priority tasks of the pharmaceutical industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Particular attention is given to the production of high-tech medicinal products that meet modern quality and safety requirements. This area is especially important in the context of the rational use of national production potential and reducing dependence on foreign supplies. In psychiatry and neurology, the introduction of modern antidepressant medicines is a key aspect of import substitution. The development of combined preparations offers additional opportunities to improve the effectiveness of depression therapy and to expand the range of domestically produced dosage forms.

Objective of the study. The purpose of this work was to create combined antidepressant tablets that are convenient to use, possess high bioavailability, and remain stable during storage. The active ingredients included mirtazapine, venlafaxine hydrochloride, as well as dry extracts of lemon balm (*Melissa officinalis*) and peppermint (*Mentha piperita*).

Materials and methods. In the development of the "Vinamir" tablet technology, active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) and excipients were used in compliance with the requirements of the State Pharmacopoeia of the Republic of Uzbekistan (SP RUz), as well as relevant regulatory and technical documentation (GOST, OST, TU). The tablets were produced using direct compression without a granulation stage, which shortens the process and reduces costs but imposes high requirements on the quality of the initial substances. The technological properties of substances and excipients were analyzed using Erweka equipment (Germany). Particle size was determined by microscopy with the VideoTest program. Selection of excipients considered their solubility, stability, compressibility, ability to ensure rapid and complete release of active substances, and the formation of mechanically strong tablets. Various combinations of excipients were tested to optimize the formulation. The study involved calcium carbonate, methylcellulose, polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), glucose, lactose, sucrose, potato and corn starch, microcrystalline cellulose, carboxymethylcellulose, magnesium stearate, calcium stearate, stearic acid, and other substances. In total, more than twenty formulations were examined. The quality of the obtained samples was assessed in accordance with current regulatory documentation.

Results. Experimental samples of combined tablets were obtained by direct compression. However, their properties proved unsatisfactory: the mass adhered to the compression tooling, and the samples did not meet the requirements for disintegration and friability. Despite testing more than twenty excipient combinations, satisfactory results were not achieved.

Conclusions. Tablets produced by direct compression did not comply with the requirements of the State Pharmacopoeia of the Republic of Uzbekistan for solid dosage forms. To achieve the necessary quality parameters, further studies are required using alternative technologies (such as wet or dry granulation), which would allow obtaining optimal pharmaceutical and technological characteristics of the "Vinamir" preparation.